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W.B YEATS CULTURAL FOUNDATION ATTAINING LIBERTY

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Abstract:

Founding a cultural pillar is a dream of W.B Yeats. As an Irish, his sown seed through his writing paves the way of attaining freedom and strengthening the root of cultural exposure. He thinks that without the concept of cultural freedom a country can hardly cross over the barrier of suppression towards independence. His thought, writing, and involvement with political leaders or in politics contribute much to the achievement of sovereignty. It is felt that he stirs the mind of Irish people through which they move the wheel of liberty and snatch victory also with their dedication and sacrifice for their motherland. He is also a true country lover building the concept of cultural identity and helps attaining the freedom of Ireland.

Keywords: culture, dedication, liberty, motherland, Yeats

Introduction:

The achievement of emancipation requires cultural involvement is perhaps the most significant idea of setting up cultural fulfillment by William Butler Yeats. His creation, poetry, plays, and cultural structure can be said best suited to the independence of Ireland. Thus he thinks of the individual identity of a cultural Ireland. His involvement with political leaders as if he were a man of politics besides a poet, a writer, or a playwright. He understands that any movement against any tyranny is incomplete without the freedom of culture. The idea proves very clear to everyone when Ireland gets her freedom indeed. Yeats is right enough to deepen the appearance of culture. His poetries not only inspire the revolutionist but also all the sons of Ireland. He remarkably uses the advent of myth, folklore, and tradition of Ireland to exhibit the importance of culture. Bernard is right about the freedom of opinion and duty for their country which is inspired by Yeats' writing. Bernard's saying in these lines is easily found.

“The Irish are a rational and intellectual people who possess the ability to participate in a measured and deliberate debate. They support

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the free expression of ideas and their authority comes from a consensus derived from discussion rather than by decree from the Crown or its representatives in the censor's office or in Dublin Castle". (Bernard, Page-16)

The strengthening of freedom of Ireland is possible for the foundation of literature and cultural identity. W.B Yeats knows it well and he contributes indeed to his culture and helps inspire to get Ireland, independent. His creation in every step, a milestone, for the golden achievement of emancipation, from the colonial curse. Ireland has become a country losing her true cultural identity which Yeats tries to restore through his great literary work making a symphony between the paths of rebellion against the British rule and restoring Irish true cultural folk, myth, and so on. Rashedulislam really comments on the use of the following traits of Yeats 'writing.

"W.B Yeats is one of the greatest lyric poets of the English Language. Yeats started his poetic career by writing is poetic plays. His philosophical ideas are expressed through the careful use of myth, symbols, and Imagery. Yeats was a master of the visual symbol. The emotional element and the symbols that drive in the poem". (Islam,Page-365)

Mainly, it is understood from the lifelong work of Yeats giving a touch of Ireland's culture based on her history too. In his many writing, he pours the water on Irish independence to activate the vigor for

snatching freedom from the hand of the British ruler.

"Cuchulain fight with the sea" is a complete masterpiece of Yeats which invokes the rebel (the freedom seeker) the resemblance with the activity of the revolutionists. The presentation of Cuchulain by Yeats is remarkable in that the poem has two sides have been shown by Yeats first, is that it has the trait of culture and the second is that it is quite similar to the revolutionists who are inspired and fight like that of Cuchulain.

Cuchulain's fight with the sea is a fight with his subconscious to control his inner hatred and conflict. The math Yeats weaves to tie the building with the cultural essence and smoothen the path of freedom of Ireland. Though he was partially a direct politician or a revolutionist who can take part in contemporary activities to get the victory, he indeed thinks about the torment of his country and peeling of the independence by the British ruler. He also bears the notion of emancipation from British rule still making the preservation of Irish cultural and traditional achievement. He knows so he continues his writing keeping the strong base strong. He can separate himself to write using the Irish myth, unlike the British writers who use the myth and history of Greek or Roman based on these cultures. In this sense, he can be called a torchbearer for the promotion of Irish folk, history, and most importantly the culture. For this reason Creed says the following things about the use of myth, legend, and folklore

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“Yeats also believed that the Irish writer should promote national literature that would serve as a response to British stereotypes concerning the barbarity of the Irish. By using myth, legend, and folklore as source material” (Creed, Page-194)

If the life span of W.B Yeats is kept in a division, there may be found four stages of Yeats regarding his works. In every stage, his work has been well discussed and criticized as well as getting much appreciation. However, in “The Second Coming”, the whole poem moves around the concept of Ireland, the history may match with the contemporary idea of Ireland which Yeats perceives here " Turning and turning in the widening gyre The falcon cannot hear the falconer"(Yeats, Page-70) the above-mentioned lines show the history of Christianity mixed with Ireland and the position of politics in Ireland and the carelessness of Irish people.

Another great creation of W.B Yeats is "No Second Troy" which depicts the beauty of his lover Maud Gonne who is an active revolutionist and marries another fighter John McBride rejecting Yeats. Their couple's life does not go a long way and they divorce but the history of Ireland and the role of activist have been started clearly. Yeats is fully motivated by the mythic essence of Troy comparing with Ireland.

In the analysis of the history of the Ireland revolution, it can easily be guessed that culture has truly helped the motto of

conquering freedom from the British as an independent nation. His base of writing is Irish folk and myth that gather the strength of cultural base required for the attainment of independence."September 19" is also another superb invention of W.B Yeats. Here he deliberately writes " Romantic Ireland dead and gone, It's with O'Leary in the grave"(Yeats, Page-44) from the above lines it is quite evident that Ireland has lost her grace and the name of legendary O'Leary has been respected here stating fourth times by whom Yeats is quite influenced. In every sphere in his writing, he has somehow managed to pour the touch of his beloved Ireland and show the concept of culture in it as if it were him. It is known to all that any writing bears the foundation of a culture. Pierce tells about the importance of literature as a part of culture written by Yeats in his article the following statements

“Arranging the scene in upbeat fashion helps foster the idea that those embarking on a course in modern Irish literature should quite properly spend time reflecting on this literary and cultural explosion, and almost immediately questions surface about cultural and other issues” (Pierce, Page-2)

Is Yeats a political person or a cultural activist? : What if it is talked about in the poem" An Irish Airman Foresees his Death" here it is purely seen that on the battlefield the Irish aviator participates not for his country because he knows, he is in the British army and if he dies his country

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won't get any benefit as well as he won't be regarded as a hero dies protecting his country, the theme of the poem expressed like Yeats is the spokesman and his inner depth anguish about the political turmoil of Ireland. He shows sacrificing in this way won't bring any glory or freedom for Ireland. After the publication of "Fairy and Folk Tales" of the Irish Peasantry ad. In 1888 He also joins the Esoteric Section of the Theosophical society. In 1891 in October he and John O'Leary organize a meeting of the Young Ireland League to unite various literary societies. In May 1892 Irish Fairy Tales ad. is published also founded Irish literary society in Dublin in the inauguration meeting in August. In 1892 "The Countess Kathleen and various Legend" is published. He also publishes in March 1895 "A Book of Irish Verse (ad)" in 1897 when he meets Lady Gregory, a renowned member of Gaelic, she inspires Yeats to write about Irish core subjects. It is like pour 'Ghee, a kind of oil, on Yajna, while setting up of Abby Theatre, Ireland's National theater he stages his play "Cathleen ni Houlihan, a nationalist play" showing Yeats support to raise the cultural identity of Ireland in a political wrapping. Even he is fully concerned after the Irish Civil War for the wreckage of the govt organization as he is in the committee.

When W.B. Yeats mother, Susan, protests riots in Dublin in March. At that time Maud Gonne is involved. Her mother sends Alister Crowley to seize Golden

Dawn Headquarter then W.B. Yeats and others repel him. W.B. Yeats marries Georgie Hyde Lees who converts her name to George Yeats. In 1918 W.B. Yeats and George Yeats move to Oxford and in January "Per Amica Silenlia Lunae essay is published. Robert George, Lady George's son is killed in an action in Italy. Yeats in Galway to supervise the restoration of Thoor Ballylce and makes it ready. In the general election, Sinn Fein wins a majority of seats in Ireland does not sit at Westminster and sets up Dail Eireann, Assembly of Ireland. In 1919, January at the first meeting the independence of Ireland is declared. In 1921, it may seem difficult that he is political and non-political. In 1928 he publishes "The Tower" which contains the theme of a pure political poem. When he publishes "Micheal Robaries and the Dancer", a collection, in 1921 before the publication of The Tower, stirs all proving the birth of modern Irish nationalism in the greatest poem fully related to Irish nationalism above all the famous phrase "a terrible beauty is born"(Yeats, Page-66) referring to the moment of birth of Ireland. Despite all, he always keeps the notion of the establishment of the cultural foundation of Ireland, and thus he writes relying on this motto. The little discussion exposes the involvement of politics in a cultural pocket.

In the other poems, Yeats has delineated the pattern of Irish culture with an experienced hand. He quite mourns for the lack of artistic woman and in especially. He mentions the rescue of culture, art, and puts huge importance" It can't grow by an

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inch or an ounce" in this line the hopelessness of culture told by Yeats is purely stated. Yeats also writes in another famous creation "The Second Coming" about political anarchy. Because of the revolution of Irish civilization which is the major concern of Yeats so he emphasizes much on the building and foundation of Irish culture resulting in the independence of free Ireland from the dominance of British rule. He creates the famous poems relating to the spur of the political momentum as well as advising to the restore or deterioration of culture so he boldly exposes the condition of the culture of Ireland. Yeats's main theme of his creation can be Irish folklore, mythology, craving for fairyland, Irish art-history, rise and fall of Irish civilization, some mysticism, failure and gaining of love as well mostly as Irish politics and nationalism. These shake his life so much and he even depicts them finely in his writing. All the discussion about the cultural establishment of W.B Yeats in his writings smoothening the road of attaining victory is not futile but successful. The most glorious invention of W.B Yeats can surely be the birth of "Easter 1916". It commonly suits this article because as it is attached to the core concept of Yeats respect is shown to the brave soil son of Ireland and also shows the establishing cultural entity likely. What idea is found is quite convincing. In the writing of Hutchinson, it is guessed the appearance of politics.

“Although political nationalism with its mass mobilizing strategies against the state has been much analyzed,

cultural nationalism- generally perceived as an enthusiasm of coteries of intellectuals – has received little scholarly attention”. (Hutchinson, Page-2)

In his writing, he glorifies the person to whom Ireland is ever indebted. George Lady Augusta, Johan O’Leary, Maud Gonne, Ann, Major Robert Gregory are prominent. He is encouraged by them and feels to ignite the spark of freedom through his writing, a cultural trait, how he contributes to the attainment of victory is cultural fulfillment. He thinks the only culture can raise the history, sing the unsung song of the heroes and embroider the myth and folklore of Ireland indeed. Thus he relies on the development of culture for the achievement of emancipation.

The main concept of this paper is not exhibited on this platform before either. And it can be so convincing to the rest of the readers raising the characteristics of the systems further not raised at all in these circumstances. Studying a poet's work is always a great effort to bring out the inner unexposed mystery. Here the analysis of the work of one of the greatest poets like W.B Yeats is truly fascinating. The collection of all the evidence and arrangement of the stages are some attempt to raise the research paper on a remarkable level. Thus the use of various journals and information from the web can be said best help. Yeats's craft of writing in the field of literature has helped to discover W.B Yeats anew. He grows old so his creation of writing got deep and

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strengthened which gathers huge appreciation highlighted in the paper. He also expresses the foundation of human culture using symbols, images, and traits of folklore. In the poem ' Among School Children" he writes the above fact deliberately.

Conclusion: The exposure of cultural entity for the support of achieving victory has been a prominent measure taken by W.B Yeats. Yeats is very much inspired by the great poet Edmund Spenser, William Blake, and P.B. Shelly. He is very much interested in Irish folklore He is the man who is in the committee of the first design of Irish currency. He develops Gaelic culture in his writing besides he writes Irish literature in English. Yeats has covered the gap between Catholic and Protestant and brings them into arts. Yeats is used in the speech of Barack Obama, Bill Clinton, etc. He keeps deep faith in writing the concept of culture and it is his main pursuit mainly. So he runs his idea much about culture than participating in politics. Though he contributes to the attainment of liberty. His involvement is quite clear; he stands erected as a political leader also as the torchbearer of cultural profoundness. This very idea has a notion that cultural motivation is a primary sensitivity of pouring the clear water in the root of a tree named liberty. The poignant of his respect for the heroes of Ireland becoming a free nation comes as a pure notion of cultural depth.

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